

Patterns and Strategies of Pokdarwis of Krapyak Seyegan Village in Improving Superior Human Resources

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ABSTRACT

The tourism awareness group is one of the supporters of village progress whose aim is to increase human resources. The Pokdarwis which was held in Krapyak Seyegan Village carried out various efforts to improve the quality of residents in the tourism sector. For this reason, various methods are taken to create a better tourist village. So this research is the result of an analysis of Pokdarwis patterns and strategies using qualitative descriptive analysis. The results of this research obtained strategies for increasing human resources in terms of tourism management and innovation. The pattern that is built is to prioritize local wisdom as the main source in determining the output to be marketed. The output obtained is in the form of organizational management and improving the quality of human resources as creators and facilitator.

INTRODUCTION

The development of tourist villages is one of the national development strategies that are quite effective in building community welfare. Therefore, it is possible that this tourist village is popular with the community as a source of good fortune and makes it a prosperous village to meet their daily needs. The existence of this tourist village has attracted the attention of researchers about how to make a village that was initially unknown become a well-maintained village and become a destination for tourists from both local and overseas (Purnawati, 2021).

Based on the results of research that has been carried out, it turns out that tourist villages that receive an increasing number of tourists are villages that package tourism products with unique characteristics from each region (Ciptosari et al., 2022). This makes tourists curious because it has less competitiveness. Efforts made to explore village potential need to be accompanied by experienced experts. So that it can create a planned tourist village. This is because, in a tourist village, there needs to be an increase in both natural resources and human resources (Yulianah, 2021).

One of the parties who can help increase tourist villages is people who are aware of the importance of village development. They are a group aware of tourist villages or what are often called pokdarwis (Purnawati, 2021). The tourist village awareness group is part of community service to help develop villages into tourist villages. This service is carried out by preparing plans for tourism products. This often happens in universities such as the Faculty of Education and Psychology, Yogyakarta State University with the Polaris in the village of Krapyak Seyegan, Sleman. This tourist village in Krapyak Seyegan Sleman was chosen to be one of the villages assisted by Yogyakarta State University which is prepared to become a tourist village.

According to the results of an initial survey conducted by the UNY FIPP Pokdarwis which was supported by interviews with residents, the potential possessed by Kampung Emas Krapyak Seyegan Tourism Village is that there is a lack of awareness among residents of the potential of this village. This is an important point for the community and the Pokdarwis who are tasked with serving there. So, with this pokdarwis, it is hoped that it can increase human resources, especially the awareness of residents in improving the Krapyak Seyegan Gold Village tourist village for the better.

METHODOLOGY

Community service research by Pokdarwis was carried out using a qualitative descriptive method by looking at the initial conditions and then identifying the process and the output produced. In the process of searching for

this data, various methods were carried out to carry out a strategy to increase human resources in Krapyak Seyegan. The methods used in data search are FGD, practice, interviews, and documentation to obtain data from various parties. The data obtained is then used as a reference in improving human resources so that they can support the progress of tourist villages.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Seyegan Emas Village Tourism Village

The tourist village of Kampung Emas Krapyak Seyegan is a village not far from the Seyegan sub-district. This village is an area with a green area which still has a fairly large rice field area with sufficient water. This village is not very big, but it contains potential that can benefit the entire community. This can be seen from the potential of the nine blessings it has.

Of the nine blessings, they consist of (1) Mendo Blessing whose focus is on livestock activities consisting of raising goats and rabbits. Next, namely (2) Mino Berkah, which is the mainstay of fisheries for mud carp, tilapia and catfish. In (3) Berkah Poultry activities are carried out to raise chickens. (4) Berkah Culinary has a focus on the culinary sector such as *angkringan* and market snacks. (5) Berkah Sports in Gold Village has sports facilities along with activities in badminton, volleyball, tennis, outbound and pencak silat. The next advantage in Krapyak is (6) Art of Blessing, which develops gamelan and Sinden artistic activities and utilizes the *joglo* area for artistic activities. Next, (7) Tahu Blessing, which is a typical *kayak* culinary tofu. In (8) Syaur, Fruit, Tani Berkah, rice production activities, various kinds of vegetables and various fruits. And the last one is (9) Blessing Education, namely all educational activities at Kmapung Emas.

After surveying the Krapyak village, of course, there were several things that Pokdarwis paid attention to, namely the lack of optimization of management and human resources who still lacked the awareness to explore potentially more deeply to become a community that was ready for the village tourism activities. Meanwhile, human resources in tourist villages are an urgency in tourism development and management (Yatmaja, 2019). For this reason, the tourism awareness group from FIPP UNY has carried out several plans to improve human resources to become superior human resources and ready to enter tourism.

The pattern built by Pokdarwis in improving human resources

The FIPP UNY tourism awareness group is a group of lecturers and students who are determined to help develop tourist villages that have expertise in the field of education. So that the pattern developed for improving human resources is carried out educationally and practically so that it can be easily accepted by the community.

The pattern used in this research is to maximize the old pattern in the potential of a tourist village into a new pattern with new products too. In this way, the potential you have will not be wasted but will be utilized more so that you will have new patterns as a result of the output used.

Turning an old pattern into a new pattern certainly requires quite a long process. For this reason, the Pokdarwis in Krapyak Seyegan will be carried out from June to September 2023. Increasing human resources, which initially lacked awareness among residents, is provided with various ways to make them better. The pattern that is built in developing human resources starts from organizing by paying attention to organizational management that is by the main tasks of each division. This is because there is no organization in the Krapyak tourism village and there is a need for guidance regarding the main duties of each member for the smooth running of an event.

This organizational management process is carried out through FGDs with residents, Pokdawris, and inviting experts from tourism to find out what is needed in a tourism organization. Then data was obtained regarding management and membership in the implementation of preparations for accepting Nine Blessings outbound participants in the Krapyak tourist village. Apart from the organizational management process, what is needed in this case is an improvement in people's mindset. This is done by paying attention to the quality of human resources to become facilitators and innovators. This is done by providing special training and strategies to motivate the community. The training carried out is as follows.

- 1) Training to explore local potential
- 2) Organizational management training
- 3) Training to be a good facilitator

The training carried out is by expert lecturers in the fields of tourism villages, management, and expertise in assisting outbound guides. From this training, young people who were initially unable to manage an event became knowledgeable about their respective duties in an event. Then the youth as facilitators can become guides during the event. This shows the success of the training carried out. In this training to explore local potential, young people were invited to innovate products, starting with an FGD about the potential of the Krapyak tourist village, which then resulted in innovative educational activities for children through educational outbound activities accompanied by a coloring program on bags with the Nine Blessings motif and batik activities. with a motif of nine blessings made simply for children. This is a unique product that is packaged to give an attractive impression to participants without leaving behind the potential of the tourist village. This is one of the successes of increasing human resources in the Krapyak tourist village by Pokdarwis.

This pattern can be seen in the picture below, which shows the existence of an old pattern by providing a process in the form of training to create a new pattern by having innovative products in a tourist village.

Figure 1. Pokdarwis pattern in improving human resources in Krapyak Tourism Village

Strategy to increase superior human resources in Krapyak Seyegan Village

Every new thing is provided with a certain strategy so that it can be implemented on target (Sultani & Aslami, 2023). The strategy for attracting tourist attention is not only good nature and potential, but the services provided will also influence tourism (Marques & Santos, 2014). This is done by Pokdarwis in increasing human resources, not only through training but also by approaching the community with tourist village appreciation activities that invite young people to visit the Pindul Gunung Kidul tourist village. The goal is to learn together to become a guide who learns from not knowing to become an expert. Apart from learning from expert guidance, in this case, the youth have carried out direct or concrete learning. This is one of the new strategies from Pokdarwis to provide direct experience so that people can understand the concept of tourism more easily (Rohyani et al., 2019).

Figure 2. Appreciation of Tourism Village Management in Pindul Cave, Gunung Kidul

Apart from the appreciation carried out by the Pokdarwis, the provision of training which is carried out with the ultimate goal of practice, is a challenge in itself for the community. Not only is knowledge provided, but experience in the village itself will make it easier to understand the potential of the village through the self-development of the community itself (Busyra et al., 2023).

The training provided is also through exploring local potential, so this is also one of the Pokdarwis' strategies for increasing the potential of human resources by knowing what is in their environment. This is because local development is also a powerful force in village development (Tomasi et al., 2020). So the importance of awareness to care about this tourist village is a concern and funds can increase human resources to become superior in the tourism sector from the results of this research.

Figure 3. Training for Krapyak Village youth in exploring the potential of the Tourism Village

Training human resources by producing products and having good facilitators is also a marketing strategy. This is because good products and good packaging, namely by providing trained facilitators, make visitors comfortable when traveling (Saputra & Bahrn, 2023).

CONCLUSION

Village tourism is not only about the beauty of the village, but village management is an important thing to pay attention to. This management requires human resources who understand tourism. For this reason, new patterns and strategies are needed to improve human resources. As in the pattern and strategy of the Pokdarwis in Krpyak Seyegan village, human resources are increased through appreciation, training and practice. From these stages to producing a human mindset that understands tourist villages, and fosters an innovative spirit in management and product development.

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